
A STUDY OF LAND USE AND LAND COVER OF LATUR DISTRICT

(M.S.)

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Abstract:

The Study has been conducted in latur district land use and land cover of study in geography is fruitful in many ways, to study of land use and land cover the present study based on secondary source. The published sources are revenue record, socio-economic abstract of Latur district, census handbook, journals etc.

Keywords: *Land Use and Land cover, Agricultural, Physiographical area etc.*

Introduction:

Agricultural is one of the older and most important avocation of the word. Human civilization and cultures evolved based on the natural resources available in a given environment. Such as plants, animals, soil, water and air. The Human community is dependent on Agricultural for foods, clothing, and Shelters even today. Conservation and management of these natural resource in a sustainable way is the need of the day and is a pre-requisite to improve the life of the people. The major agricultural products can be broadly grouped into foods, fibers, fuels, and raw materials. Food classes include cereals, vegetables, fruits, oils, meat, milk, eggs,

and fungi. Over one-third of the world's workers are employed in agriculture.

Objectives:

The Main objectives of the present Paper are followings.

- 1) To study Geographical area.
- 2) To study land use land cover category in Latur district.

Methodology of Study Area:

The present study is based on primary and secondary source, agriculture department in Latur district. District gazetteers, district statistical department, Census handbooks, socio economic review

(2011-2021), and district statistical abstract of Study region district.

the eastern side of the Latur is Bidar district of Karnataka, whereas Nanded is on the northeast, Parbhani on the northern side, Beed on the Northwest and Osmanabad on the western and southern side. The entire district of Latur is situated on the Balaghat plateau, 540 to 638 meters from the mean sea level.

Geographical Study:

The Latur District is in the south-eastern part of the Maharashtra state. Latur town is situated on the 18.7° latitude and 73.25° longitude. The district is situated on the Maharashtra Karnataka boundary. On

Map: Location in Latur District

Result and Discussion:

Sr. No	Land use Category	Total Area (In Hectares)		Percentage		Changes
		2011	2021	2011	2021	
		2011	2021			
1	Net sown Area	583802	609029	81.57	85.17	3.6
2	Other Land	59991	32703	8.38	4.57	-3.81
3	Cultivable waste	20730	22203	2.89	3.10	0.21
4	Barren and Uncultivated	18767	10748	2.62	1.50	1.12
5	Land not available waste	10253	25077	1.43	3.50	-2.07
6	Forest	3511	4166	0.49	0.58	0.09
Total Geographical Area		715700	715054	100	100	

Source: Socio-Economic Abstract in Latur District-2011-2021.

Conclusion:

The discussion in above mentioned text indicates spatial-temporal distribution of general land use for Latur district the total area in study region has 70 percentage of net snow area. This net snow area is slightly exceeded then Latur distract and Maharashtra state. The net

snow area has increased from south to west with increasing fertility and irrigation only. Also in non-agricultural sector it was 2.62 in 2011. And it has now come down to 1.12 in 2021. Compared to 2011, there has been a decrease in 2021. Also, there is an increase in the forest area in Latur district. As it increased by 0.09 in 2021

Dr. Omprakash. V. Shahapurkar & Mr. Pradip G. Gorambekar

compared to 2011, it shows a positive outlook. East part has slowly increased net snow area rapidly due to undulating and region. (2011-2021) from the total net snow area. At the same time, the net area to the east appears to be somewhat less. The proportion of other lands has also decreased in 2021 as compared to 2011. It is decreased currently at -3.81. All the categories in the general land use have direct impact on the net snow area and hence this distribution is of prime important.

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